

QUIZ**LAST NAME: FIASORGBOR****FIRST NAME: NUTIFAFA KODZO****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 7)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- In carrying out doctoral study at Euclid University, students are advised to either use UK or US spellings and punctuations but must be consistent in the usage of the chosen variant of the English language. Which of the following statements is true?**
 - Punctuations inside quotation marks are optional in US English.
 - Punctuations outside quotation marks are optional in UK English.
 - Punctuations are placed within the quotation marks for US English.¹**
 - Punctuations are placed within the quotation marks for UK English.
- Plagiarism is an academic offence and students must endeavour at all times to avoid it. Plagiarism occurs when the writer uses someone's**

¹ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: EUCLID University. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019), 59.

information or idea, but fails to cite the source of the information. What are the two main forms of citation?

- List of work citation and quotation.
- In-text and list of works cited.**²
- Quotation and in-text citation.
- List of work citation, in-text citation and quotation.

3. Research works are usually undertaken to address a problem by asking relevant questions. The nature of these questions vary depending on the purpose of the research. What type of questions are commonly asked in academic research?

- Conceptual questions.**³
- Practical question.
- Applied question.
- Academic question.

4. A writer using bibliography-style citation will be most concerned about the usage of which of the following?

- Headnote and startnote.
- Endnote and startnote.
- Footnote and endnote.**⁴

² EUCLID, 15.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

⁴ Turabian, 50.

Footnote and headnote.

5. **The order of elements in reference list entries follows the general pattern: author, date, title, facts of publication. What is the order of elements in notes and bibliography list entries?**

Author, title, facts of publication.⁵

Author, facts of publication, title, date.

Author, date, title.

Author, date, facts of publication, title.

6. **A number of punctuations are used in both US and UK English. Which of the under listed punctuations is used to separate items within a sentence, including clauses, phrases, and individual words?**

Commas.⁶

Period.

Colon.

Dashes.

7. **Terms can be shortened in several ways. Terms shortened to only the first letters of each word and pronounced as a single word are called acronyms. What is the name of an abbreviation pronounced as a series of letters such as EU or USA?**

Contraction.

Shorthand.

⁵ Turabian, 92.

⁶ Turabian, 173.

- Initialism.**⁷
- All of the above.
8. **A research approach can be either qualitative or quantitative. What are the two main factors that determine the choice of research approach to be used?**
- Research problem and purpose.**⁸
- Research problem and methodology.
- Research purpose and methodology.
- All of the above.
9. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe, the introductory section of a research serves three major purposes, in exception of which of the following?**
- Provide a summary of the research findings.**⁹
- Provides context and purpose of the study.
- Identifies the research questions and research approach to be adopted.
- Provides the rationale and significance of the study.
10. **Which section of a qualitative dissertation includes an overview of the research design, information needed and sources of data, proposed**

⁷ Turabian, 196.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 33.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 18.

research sample, plans and methods for data collection and data analysis, and a rationale for the procedures to be used?

- Literature review section.
- Data analysis and reporting findings section.
- Research design and data analysis.
- Methodology section.**¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 19.